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there's
something
science
can do.

Issue Tracker 2025/003
March 17, 2025

DOGE quietly decreases savings estimate for 30 terminated FDA leases: The Department of Government Efficiency (DOGE) continues to reduce government spending, including terminating the leases for 30 FDA facilities, though has revised the savings from those cancelled leases specifically from \$660M to \$468M. Budget cuts are also curtailing the NIH's ability to engage with domestic research collaborators, including barring employees from filing new patent applications and licensing existing patents.

Congress Re-Introduces EPIC Act to Remove IRA's 'Pill Penalty': Bipartisan representatives in the US have introduced a bill called the Ensuring Pathways to Innovative Cures (EPIC) Act, that would increase the time before a small molecule can be subject to price negotiations under the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) from 9 to 13 years. The IRA currently gives small molecule drugs nine years before they can be put up for negotiations, whereas biologics only become eligible for price negotiations after 13 years. The effect will be to maintain higher drug prices for an additional 4 years on small molecules.

Pfizer convinces US Patent Office to cancel two Moderna COVID-19 vaccine patents: Pfizer and BioNTech have successfully convinced the US Patent Office that two mRNA vaccine technology patents that Moderna had accused them of infringing were invalid due to prior art and being overly broad. On the same day, a German court ruled that Pfizer and BioNTech had infringed the European Moderna patent and ordered both companies to pay yet undetermined damages.

Researchers Part of OpenRxiv Launch to Secure the Future of Open Science: Yale, in collaboration with Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory and The BMJ, launched openRxiv, an independent nonprofit organization overseeing bioRxiv and medRxiv, two online preprint servers for life and health sciences. Established in 2013 and 2019 respectively, these platforms allow researchers to share early versions of their studies prior to peer review, accelerating scientific communication and collaboration. The creation of openRxiv aims to ensure the long-term sustainability and independence of these servers, promoting open science practices and fostering global collaboration.